

Green Concrete Innovation: Utilizing Bamboo Leaf Ash and Goat Hair for Eco-Friendly and Sustainable Construction

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Abstract

Concrete is a vital material in modern construction, yet Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), its main ingredient, contributes significantly to carbon emissions due to its high energy consumption. This study explores an eco-friendly alternative by partially replacing OPC with Bamboo Leaf Ash (BLA) and reinforcing concrete with Goat Hair (GH), a natural fiber. BLA and GH are agro-wastes typically discarded but possess environmental and structural potential.

Concrete mixes were prepared with 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% BLA, and GH content of 0.4%, 0.5%, and 0.6% by cement weight. A total of 70 cube specimens (150 mm × 150 mm × 150 mm), 30 cylinders (150 mm × 300 mm) and 18 beams (100 mm × 100 mm × 500 mm) were tested following ASTM C39, C496 and C78 standards.

Results showed that sample with 5% BLA and 0.5% GH (C-5-0.5) exhibited a balanced performance with 33.20 MPa compressive strength, 3.47 MPa split tensile strength (26% higher than control), and 4.17 MPa flexural strength (28% higher than control). Excessive fiber (0.6% GH) or BLA (>10%) tended to reduce strength due to poor dispersion and ash reactivity.

The study supports using agricultural waste to produce sustainable concrete with reduced cement use and enhanced tensile performance. Future research should focus on microstructural analysis, durability, and fiber dispersion optimization to enhance performance consistency. This solution promotes green construction and is ideal for regions with accessible bamboo and goat farming.

Keywords: *agro-waste, bamboo leaf ash (BLA), eco-friendly materials, goat hair (GH), ordinary portland cement (OPC), sustainable construction*